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Dependency on Various Signal Frequency Bands for Partial Discharge Signal Detection and PD Source Positioning in Power Transformer

Djordje DUKANAC*

**Joint Stock Company “Elektromreza Srbije” (EMS JSC) Belgrade
Serbia**

Functionality of Electric Power System and Equipment

djordje.dukanac@ems.rs

SUMMARY

Power transformers are a crucial part of the electric power system. To achieve a resilient electric power system, power transformers should be investigated for eventual defects. Partial discharge (PD) occurs in high-voltage equipment such as power transformers when electrical insulation has deteriorated due to discontinuities or imperfections (e.g., sharp points, voids, or gas bubbles) in the insulation system. PDs degrade transformer insulation in time, and if not interrupted, can lead to complete transformer failure. So, measuring PDs helps in the early detection, repair, and maintenance of power transformers. Several methods are used to detect PD signals and locate their source, one of which is the ultra-high frequency (UHF) based technique. PD signals can originate from various source types and be detected in a large frequency range. According to the Cigré brochure, the best frequency range for detecting PD signals in a power transformer is between 100 MHz and 1 GHz; other studies have found that this range is between 400 MHz and 900 MHz. This study aims to analyse and compare the effects of various input excitation pulse frequency ranges (EFRs), the transformer tank, the active components of the transformer, and the total efficiency of the used antenna on the characteristics of received UHF PD signals at sensors and on the positioning of the PD source, which is both important for power transformer preventive maintenance. Analysed characteristics of UHF PD signals at sensors included: their waveforms, times of arrivals (TOAs) and magnitudes of their first peaks (FPs), time differences of arrivals (TDOAs), and magnitude ratios between the extreme amplitudes and FPs in the first wave packets, and changes in their amplitude spectra. Influences of reflected waves incorporated in the received signals were also analysed. Because of difficulties in achieving these analyses on a real transformer in operation or an experimental transformer where the PD source is unknown or difficult to be temporarily mounted in transformer winding, simulations were done using a power transformer model made by the Ansys HFSS software. These simulations involved all reflections and diffractions caused by the transformer's internal structure. The four UHF sensors (dipole antennas) were used to record and plot the EM UHF signals emitted by the fifth antenna used as a PD source. FP method was used for the PD source positioning.

KEYWORDS

Excitation frequency range (EFR), first peak (FP), internal transformer structure, partial discharge (PD), PD signal, PD source, power transformer, time difference of arrival (TDOA), time of arrival (TOA), ultra-high frequency (UHF).

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1 INTRODUCTION

Electrical power transmission and distribution systems depend heavily on power transformers. The insulation of power transformers ages with time, and anomalous environmental activity, including mechanical, electrical, and chemical stressors, hasten this process. Partial discharge (PD), a localized breakdown of insulation materials in power transformers, is a significant problem that can lead to catastrophic failure if not detected on time. Released energies from partial discharges (PDs), such as light, heat, and electromagnetic waves, are prevented from passing through the metal case, so they must be detected by the internal sensor [1]. The insensitivity to on-site external noises is one benefit of operating under the ultra-high frequency band [2].

The causes of PD are briefly described below [3]:

- Creeping flashover, or surface discharge, at the oil-pressboard interface that is regarded as a serious insulation system failure in power transformers
- Free particles in transformer oil that can be either mobile conducting or non-conducting particles
- A metal object at a floating potential if it no longer has contact with the grounding or winding, which can be present inside a power transformer
- Delamination of the solid insulation interfaces, cracking onset in solid insulation (oil-immersed paper or pressboard), or cavities (between layers of paper or pressboard), which can all result from subpar manufacture or aging of the insulation material
- Sharp edge (protrusion) on a transformer metal object or winding can cause PD. The defect can occur during the manufacturing process or maintenance
- Gas bubbles in transformer oil, which can deteriorate the dielectric integrity of the transformer insulation system

It is frequently challenging to detect and locate PD, and the ultra-high frequency (UHF) method is one of the diagnostic techniques that has been developed. Uncertainties remain regarding the frequency range that PDs radiate and the frequency range that must be assessed in a measurement [4]. The frequency spectrum for transformer failure measurements using the UHF method is, according to the Cigré brochure, from 100 MHz to 1 GHz and, more recently, between 400 MHz and 900 MHz [5].

The antenna factors (AF) for three distinct sensor types—a UHF drain valve sensor, a UHF plate sensor, and a combined UHF/acoustic sensor—are displayed versus frequency in Figure 1 [6]. These sensors were positioned at the same insertion depth as the fixed plate sensor and mounted directly at the gigahertz transverse electromagnetic (GTEM) cell without a gate valve. The UHF plate sensor and the UHF drain valve sensor have modest AFs that are essentially similar in the frequency range of [0.125–2.250] GHz, despite their distinct designs, as Figure 1 illustrates. The sensitivity is lowest for a combined UHF/acoustic sensor, which detects two distinct waves (electromagnetic and mechanical). The AF is the ratio between the electric field strength at the antenna and the voltage at the antenna terminals. Smaller AF means higher antenna sensitivity.

Four UHF sensors installed on the transformer tank were used to identify the position of the PD source based on the first peaks' (FPs') arrival times of received signals [3]. At every power transformer's UHF sensor, the received signal, which includes PD, is influenced by the following factors [2]:

- The power transformer's internal structure, which usually determines the quickest path for VHF/UHF waves to travel between the PD source and the UHF sensor
- The transformer tank's resonant cavity, which permits certain resonant modes with powers for specific frequencies based on its size
- The location of the PD source and its specific type
- The sensor's location, radiation pattern, polarization, and frequency response

Figure 1. AFs for three different types of sensors that were directly mounted at the GTEM cell: a UHF drain valve sensor, a combined (UHF and acoustic) PD sensor (using UHF output), and a UHF plate sensor [6].

The complex solid structure of the transformer windings and the presence of mineral oil in the transformer tank make it challenging to temporarily install an antenna (supplied by an artificial pulse generator) as the artificial source for the PD signals' emission to conduct PD detection investigations on a real power transformer. In [7], for instance, four UHF antennas were installed in the holes drilled through the transformer tank to act as four PD sources. For these reasons, PD signals' propagations' simulations through the internal structure of the transformer and source location determination in the transformer model are highly suitable solutions. [8] presents a study that uses the FDTD method to investigate the propagations of UHF PD signals in power transformers. In the middle of a tank, two different obstacles—a conducting cylinder and a cuboid—have been placed in turn. Several power transformer models, ranging in complexity from simplified to composite, were employed in [1,9] to provide simulation results for the detection of PD signals at four UHF sensors. The attenuations of the PD-EM waveforms received at the UHF sensors were influenced by the receiving antennas' imperfect orientations and positions relative to the transmitter (PD source). In [10], it was demonstrated how to obtain more realistic signals utilizing a specific technique and MATLAB simulation.

In [11,12], the CST (Computer Simulation Technology) microwave studio was utilized to model a power transformer with a PD source and UHF antennas and to simulate the propagations of PD signals. In [11], Dijkstra's algorithm was used for pathfinding. A voxelized 3D simulation model of the transformer was required for the path-finding process, and a time differences of arrival (TDOAs) database was created to serve as a lookup table for measured TDOAs for localization. In [12], machine learning and deep learning techniques were used to study PD localization utilizing three sensors on a simplified steel transformer tank model.

This study aims to analyse and compare how various frequency ranges of the PD source excitation pulse, along with transmitting and receiving antennas total efficiency and the internal transformer structure, affect signal characteristics at each of the four sensors (such as waveforms, first peaks, extreme amplitudes, amplitude spectra), as well as PD source positioning. Those are both important for the power transformer preventive maintenance. Therefore, those simulations of propagations of PD UHF signals and the subsequent positioning of a PD source are very useful. The simulation model is described in Section 2. Sections 3 and 4, respectively, explain how the detected PD signals depend on several pertinent excitation pulse frequency ranges and how the PD source location in power transformers is determined using these ranges. The conclusion is presented in Section 5.

2 SIMULATION MODEL

To conduct in-depth research, the signals' propagations from the PD source to four UHF sensors were simulated using Ansys HFSS and the typical three-phase power transformer model, whose trimetric and top layouts are shown in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively. The transformer model had a stainless steel 304 tank filled with mineral oil, a three-phase low voltage (LV) and high voltage (HV) copper windings, and a three-limb four-step electrical steel magnetic core. Four UHF sensors and a PD source were modelled using five dipole antennas.

Given the tank's dimensions of 2800 mm in height, 880 mm in width, and 2300 mm in length, a small three-phase power transformer with a 66/11 kV transformation ratio and a 5 MVA total deliverable apparent power was considered. $S_1 = (65, 65, 2750)$ mm, $S_2 = (1150, 440, 2758)$ mm, $S_3 = (2235, 815, 2755)$ mm, and $S_4 = (70, 810, 2760)$ mm were the locations (centres of masses) of the receiving UHF antennas.

The transmitting antenna, which acted as the PD source, was assumed to have a centre of mass at $O = (1985, 295, 1485)$ mm. It was situated at the upper portion of the first phase of the winding, on the rear side of the first limb of the core. It was positioned nearer the LV winding, between the 37th and 38th disks of the LV winding, and between the magnetic core and LV coils as shown in Figures 2a and 2b. Figure 2c displays the 60 mm by 5 mm copper-based dipole antenna arms with a 4 mm by 5 mm port positioned in between.

Figure 2. (a) Trimetric layout of the transformer model with five antennas ($S_1, S_2, S_3,$ and S_4 are the UHF sensors, and O is the PD source). (b) The top layout of the transformer model. (c) The dipole antenna model.

Due to the limited capabilities of the computer (primarily the processor and random-access memory (RAM)) and the complexity of Ansys HFSS software and its calculations, a couple of necessary simplifications and limitations of the power transformer construction were done to perform simulations.

Firstly, the inter-insulation between adjacent turns of each of the 42 corresponding LV or HV discs in the radial direction, with a thickness of 1.2 mm, is not considered and is assumed to be copper. Each HV disk is divided into two parts along the vertical axis with a gap of 1.2 mm, although it should be composed of four parts. Neglecting the two 1.2 mm vertical gaps in each HV winding's disk results in a slightly larger signal attenuation. EM waves in mineral oil (with the dielectric constant of $\epsilon_r = 2.2$) have a wavelength of 15.51 cm at 1.7 GHz and 24.17 cm at 700 MHz, thus 1.2 mm is a tiny aperture for these waves. Every wave diffraction at such a small aperture causes the wave beam passing through it to lose intensity in different directions relative to the aperture itself, which results in a loss in signal strength from the PD source in the path shortest to a particular UHF sensor.

Secondly, the paper insulation and the pressboard inter-insulation of the three-phase LV and HV windings were considered to be mineral oil since they are both impregnated with mineral oil, which lowers their dielectric constant.

Thirdly, due to the lack of precise data and the additional complexity of the power transformer model, the following less present and influential parts were not considered: a) insulating parts such as insulating spacers, strips, bushings, etc. and b) metal parts, including screws, winding fixing parts, core clamping frames, winding leads, etc.

2.1 3D total gain polar diagrams of the transmitting antenna used as PD source at different frequencies

To perform simulations and generate 3D polar diagrams of the PD source's total gains at various frequencies for comparison, it was assumed that the transformer tank in Figure 2a's simulation model had transparent walls (i.e., radiation boundary). The PD pulses were simulated using broadband Gaussian pulses with an amplitude of 1 V for the following excitation frequency ranges (EFRs): [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz. In Figures 3 and 4, the 3D polar diagrams of the UHF dipole antenna's total gains, expressed in decibels [dB], were obtained at 700 MHz, 1 GHz, 1.5 GHz, and 1.7 GHz.

Due to the transmitting dipole antenna's design, the 3D polar diagrams of its total gains, as seen in Figures 3 and 4, significantly depart from the optimal spherical forms at the frequencies taken into consideration. A significantly greater number of zones of lower intensity of total gains are in the middle of the polar diagrams in the plane of the dipole antenna in the longitudinal direction of the antenna. The 3D polar diagrams' surfaces become less smooth as the PD source radiation frequencies increase. On the 3D polar diagrams, the largest and the smallest maximum values of the PD source total gains are 2.36 dB at 1.5 GHz and -1.79 dB at 700 MHz, respectively.

Figure 3. 3D polar diagrams of the PD source in trimetric orientation showing the total antenna gains in [dB] obtained from the simulation model in Figure 2a with transparent tank walls at different frequencies: (a) 700 MHz and (b) 1 GHz.

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Figure 4. 3D polar diagrams of the PD source in trimetric orientation showing the total antenna gains in [dB] obtained from the simulation model in Figure 2a with transparent tank walls at different frequencies: (a) 1.5 GHz and (b) 1.7 GHz.

Figure 5a shows a dipole antenna in a transparent cube filled with mineral oil with a side of 400 mm. The total antenna efficiency for the [0–1.7] GHz excitation pulse frequency range is displayed in Figure 5b utilizing frequency sweep in 601 points derived from the simulation using the model in Figure 5a. Therefore, the antenna's total efficiency peak of 0.97 appears at 750.9 MHz in the [0–1.7] GHz EFR. The total efficiency of the antenna is larger than 0.5 in the frequency range of [614.9–1034.2] MHz. For the EFRs of [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz, the weighted average frequencies are 613.4 MHz, 768.5 MHz, 937 MHz, and 1007.5 MHz, respectively. The radiation efficiency of an antenna is defined as the ratio of the power radiated by an antenna to the power fed to the excitation port of the antenna. Total radiation efficiency also includes the power lost due to poor voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) (or mismatch loss). It is a multiplication of antenna efficiency and mismatch loss.

Figure 5. (a) A dipole antenna used as the transmitting and receiving antenna in the simulation model in Figure 2a, in the centre of the transparent box filled with mineral oil with a side of 400 mm. (b) Total efficiency of the transmitting antenna versus frequency obtained from the simulation using the model in Figure 5a, in the Gaussian pulse frequency range of [0–1.7] GHz.

The same 3D polar graphs of total gains at various frequencies and the total efficiency vs frequency diagram in the [0–1.7] GHz EFR are likewise useful for the receiving antenna with the same properties as the transmitting antenna described in Section 2.

3 RESULTS

Simulations were performed using the finite element method (FEM) in Ansys HFSS. The reflections of all PD waves off the transformer tank walls, three-phase LV and HV windings, and three-phase core type magnetic core were considered. Additionally, all PD waves' diffractions around the transformer's active metal components (magnetic core and copper windings) and through the tiny spaces between the metal components of the LV and HV coils were considered.

3.1 Analysing signals at sensors originating from PD source output pulses for various EFRs

As will be shown later, the output signals at the sensors depend mainly on the characteristics and mutual orientations of the antennas, the frequency ranges of the excitation pulses, the internal structure of the transformer, and the line-of-sight (LOS) distances between PD source and the sensors.

Figure 6a shows the positive input excitation broadband Gaussian pulses at the transmitting antenna served as the PD source, at different EFRs [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz, with an amplitude of 1 V. Figure 6b shows corresponding amplitude spectra gained from the input pulses in the periods of [0.8–4.6] ns, [0.4–3.4] ns, [0.2–2.2] ns and [0–2] ns, respectively. As the EFRs expand, the pulses have earlier peaks and smaller widths, roughly proportionally to the respective frequency ranges.

Figure 6. (a) Input Gaussian PD pulses at the different EFRs at the transmitting antenna, which in Figure 2a's simulation model represents the PD source. (b) Corresponding amplitude spectra of the input pulses gained for the appropriate periods of their appearances.

From Figure 6b, the weighted average frequencies of the four input pulses at different EFRs [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz, are 196.7 MHz, 503.1 MHz, 652.9 MHz and 467.7 MHz, respectively.

Figure 7a shows signals at the output port of the transmitting antenna for the different EFRs of the pulses at the input port of the antenna. In contrast to the corresponding positive input Gaussian pulses in Figure 6a, all output signals at the transmitting antenna exhibit oscillations after the completion of their positive initial pulses. Smaller peaks, more delayed peaks, and larger deformations of the peaks of the positive initial pulses of the output excitation signals, as well as larger and more frequent oscillations after the ends of their positive initial pulses, are all consequences of respective higher input pulse frequency ranges. Even the positive initial pulses of the output signals for EFRs of [0–1.5] GHz and [0–1.7] GHz exhibit oscillations at their peaks, making them significantly wider than the corresponding positive input Gaussian pulses.

Figure 7b shows TDOAs and magnitude differences between the extreme peaks of the output signals' initial pulses and the corresponding maximal peaks of the input pulses at the transmitting antenna for different EFRs.

Figure 7. (a) Output signals at the transmitting antenna for different EFRs. (b) TDOAs and magnitude differences between the extreme peaks of the output signals and the corresponding peaks of the input pulses at the transmitting antenna.

From previous Figure 7b it can be seen that as EFR increases, the extreme peak of the output signal's initial pulse is more delayed and has more decreased magnitude in relation to the respective maximal peak of the input pulse at the transmitting antenna. In comparison to [0–1.7] GHz EFR, the TDOA and magnitude difference are 6.26 and 2 times higher than at [0–0.7], 1.57 and 1.34 times greater than at [0–1] GHz EFR, and 1.025 and 1.023 times higher than at [0–1.5] GHz EFR.

The amplitude spectra of the output signals at the transmitting antenna for the different EFRs [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz are shown in Figure 8, in the periods of [0.8–8.0] ns, [0.4–8.0] ns, [0.2–8.0] ns and [0–8] ns, respectively. As the frequency ranges of input pulses of the PD source are higher, the amplitude spectra of output excitation signals are wider, but their peak values are lower. The amplitude spectra's excitation output signals' peaks are smaller [1.9, 2.5, 3.7, and 3.9 times] than the corresponding peaks in Figure 6a's input pulse amplitude spectra at the transmitting antenna.

From Figure 8, the weighted average frequencies of the four output excitation signals for different EFRs [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz, are 230.8 MHz, 423.2 MHz, 582.8 MHz and 568.9 MHz, respectively. In relation to the weighted average frequencies of the four input pulses, differences are 34.1 MHz, -79.9 MHz, -70.1 MHz, and 101.2 MHz.

Figure 8. Amplitude spectra of output signals at the transmitting antenna for different EFRs gained from the simulation model in Figure 2a.

3.2 Analysing the output signals at the UHF sensors for the several different PD source input EFRs

The PD excitation output signals had to travel via a complex transformer design model to reach the UHF sensors. During this process, they encountered many diffractions and reflections, all of which applied simulations captured. The output signals at sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 are displayed in Figures 9a-c and 10, respectively, for the various input excitation pulse frequency ranges [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz.

From Figures 9a-c and 10 it can be seen that signal 1's first wave packet width is approximately 10 ns, signal 2's is 12.4 ns, signal 3's is roughly 9.4 ns, and Signal 4's is approximately 10 ns. Over time, the signals have been affected differently by the reflected signals from the metal parts of the transformer's internal structure since the signals first appeared at the sensors. Parts of the signals beyond their first wave packets can only be considered as the results of reflected waves.

Since signal 4 had to travel the longest and most complicated path via the internal transformer structure, it is clear that it is the most attenuated and contains the densest reflections' impacts. In signals 2 and 4, extreme amplitudes in the periods from the end of the first packets to 40 ns even exceeded the extreme amplitudes of the signals' first wave packets. In contrast, signal 3 is the least attenuated and contains the lowest reflections' impacts because it had to take the simplest and shortest path via the internal transformer construction.

Figure 9. Output signals recorded at sensors (a) 1, (b) 2, and (c) 3, which were obtained from the simulation model in Figure 2a, for different frequency ranges of input excitation pulses [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, and [0–1.5] GHz, respectively.

Figure 10. Output signals recorded at sensor 4, which were obtained from the simulation model in Figure 2a, for the frequency range of input excitation pulse of [0–1.7] GHz.

Figure 11 shows all recorded signals FPs' times of arrival (TOAs) at four UHF sensors for different input excitation pulse frequency ranges [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz.

Figure 11. Recorded signals FPs' TOAs at four UHF sensors for different input excitation pulse frequency ranges.

The FPs' TOAs of all signals at sensors are, as anticipated, largest in the [0–0.7] GHz input excitation pulse frequency range and decrease as the EFR increases. For each EFR, FPs' TOAs depend mainly on the positions of the sensors relative to the PD source.

The LOS distances between the PD source and the UHF sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 are 2.31 m, 1.53 m, 1.39 m, and 2.36 m, respectively. However, in the simulation model in Figure 2a, those distances depend also on the obstacles along the shortest paths from the PD source to the sensors. For example, the optimal ratio of TOAs of the FPs of signals 3 and 4 is 1.7 times. However, this ratio is smaller in the simulations based on the model in Figure 2a for the various input excitation pulse frequency ranges [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz, i.e., 1.5 times, 1.52 times, 1.57 times, and 1.58 times.

Figure 12 shows FPs' magnitudes of recorded signals at four UHF sensors for different frequency ranges of the input excitation pulse.

Because there are the most metal obstacles on the path from the PD source to sensor 4, signals recorded at sensor 4 have the lowest FPs for all four EFRs, as shown in Figure 12. Like sensor 4, sensor 1 is located far from the PD source. The distance from the PD source to sensor 1 is just 1.02 times shorter than that to sensor 4. However, because there are significantly fewer obstacles between the PD source and sensor 1, the FPs are considerably larger, or [11.4–26.7] times, in favour of signals at sensor 1 than those at sensor 4 for all four EFRs. Thus, signal 1 is significantly less attenuated than signal 4.

Figure 12. FPs' magnitudes of recorded signals at four UHF sensors for various input excitation pulse frequency ranges.

The two graphs in Figures 13 and 14 show, respectively, 1) TDOAs and 2) magnitudes' ratios between extreme amplitudes in the first wave packets and the FPs of the signals at sensors for different EFRs, which can be additionally influenced by reflected PD waves from the transformer's tank and active components.

When comparing signals 1, 2, 3, and 4 at sensors, Figure 13 demonstrates that the PD wave reflections from the transformer's tank and active components result in different TDOAs between the extreme amplitudes in the initial signals' packets with respect to the signals' FPs, for each EFR. Based on that, signals 2 and 4 show the greatest number of PD wave reflections, whereas signal 3 shows the fewest. The TDOAs range from [3.86–4.83] ns for signal 4, [3.52–4.78] ns for signal 2, [3.10–4.59] ns for signal 1, and [1.69–3.12] ns for signal 3. As the EFR increases, TDOAs between the extreme amplitudes in the first packets and FPs in all signals at the sensors decrease.

Figure 13. TDOAs between the extreme amplitudes in the first wave packets and FPs of the signals at UHF sensors for various input excitation pulse frequency ranges.

Figure 14 displays the magnitudes' ratios between the extreme amplitudes in the first wave packets and the FPs of the signals at four UHF sensors for different EFRs.

The considerable degree to which reflected waves impact the signals at sensor four is shown in Figure 14, for all EFRs. As a result, the magnitudes' ratios between the extreme amplitudes in the signals' first wave packets and their FPs are significantly increased in the range of [116.5–1004.7] times for different EFRs. For the other signals (at the first, second, and third sensors), the magnitudes' ratios are significantly smaller, i.e. [24.2–86.5] times, [22.7–35.5] times, and [23.3–61.2] times, respectively.

Figure 14. Magnitudes' ratios between the extreme amplitudes in the signals' first wave packets and their FPs for different input excitation pulse frequency ranges.

Figures 15 and 16a-c show amplitude spectra of the output signals at sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 in their first wave packets, respectively, for different frequency ranges of input excitation pulses [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz.

Figure 15. Amplitude spectra of the output signals recorded at sensor 1 in their first wave packets lasting about [11.9–21.9] ns, which were obtained from the simulation model in Figure 2a, for different frequency ranges of input excitation pulses [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz.

Figure 16. Amplitude spectra of the output signals recorded at sensors: a) 2, b) 3, and c) 4, in their first wave packets lasting about [8.1–20.5] ns, [7.5–16.9] ns and [12.4–22.4] ns, respectively, which were obtained from the simulation model in Figure 2a, for different frequency ranges of input excitation pulses [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz.

Figure 17 displays the weighted average frequencies for each recorded signal at four UHF sensors for various input excitation pulse frequency ranges so that the amplitude spectra of those four signals can be compared.

As shown in Figure 17, the weighted average frequencies of the four received signals taken on the period of 2.5 GHz fall into the relatively smaller ranges [654–694] MHz, [724–749] MHz, [800–837] MHz, and [837–890] MHz, in contrast to the weighted average frequencies of the output signals at PD source of 230.8 MHz, 423.2 MHz, 582.8 MHz, and 568.9 MHz, for EFRs of [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz. The output signal's weighted average frequency at the PD source for an EFR of [0–1] GHz is the closest to the half value of the EFR of [0–1] GHz when compared to other EFRs. It is evident that UHF sensors provide signals at weighted average frequencies in a limited range [654–890] MHz for this internal transformer structure and for the EFRs that were used. As a result, it is possible to conclude that the amplitude spectra of signals at four sensors are moved toward higher frequencies relative to the transmitting antenna's output excitation signals, in all EFRs. According to Figure 5b's diagram showing the transmitting and receiving antennas' total efficiency versus frequency, the weighted average frequencies for the EFRs of [0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz are, respectively, 613.4 MHz, 768.5 MHz, 937 MHz, and 1007.5 MHz. For EFR of [0–1] GHz, weighted average frequencies' range of output signals at sensors of [724–749] MHz is the nearest to the weighted average frequency of 768.5 GHz found from total efficiency diagram of the receiving antennas.

Figure 17. The weighted average frequencies for each recorded signal at four UHF sensors for various EFRs.

3.3 Analysing the average absolute location errors of PD source for several considered EFRs

Finally, the impact of the various input excitation pulse frequency ranges on determining the location of the PD source should be taken into account. The FP method was used, which is based on calculating the TDOAs between the FPs of the signals at four UHF sensors. In Figure 18, the average absolute location errors of the PD source are obtained for input PD pulses at various frequency ranges at the transmitting antenna, which simulates the PD source in Figure 2a's simulation model.

The lowest average absolute location error, 4.45 cm, was obtained when the [0–1] GHz EFR was used. The largest average absolute location error of 9.53 cm was attained with an EFR of [0–0.7] GHz.

It is commonly known that the PD signal's wavelength is 15.51 cm at 1.7 GHz and 24.17 cm at 700 MHz. Therefore, in the simulation model shown in Figure 2a, the absolute average location error may have been expected to decrease as EFR decreased because of the rising diffractions and attenuations of the signals in the shortest path from the PD source to the four sensors.

Figure 18. Calculated average absolute location errors of PD source in the cases of input PD pulses at different EFRs at the transmitting antenna, which simulates the PD source in the simulation model in Figure 2a.

In the simulation, HFSS does adaptive passes until the Delta S falls below a set threshold. Due to computer RAM constraints, the minimum Delta S value that could have been set for the EFRs [0–1.5] GHz and [0–1.7] GHz was 0.027. The average absolute location errors of the PD source were 7 cm and 7.42 cm, respectively. Computer RAM requirements increase with an increase in the EFR. However, it was enabled to set Delta S at 0.02 for the EFR of [0–1] GHz, which could have contributed to the improved accuracy of the PD source location result. The second reason could be more favourable TDOAs between FPs of the signals at sensors for [0–1] GHz EFR. Despite setting Delta S in the range of [0.002–0.027], for EFR of 0.7 GHz, the result of the average absolute location error remained the same and largest.

CONCLUSION

This article provides a detailed analysis of how the various PD source EFRs, internal power transformer structure, and antenna properties affect the PD signals received at the four UHF sensors as well as the assessment of PD source location in a power transformer. Four PD input excitation pulse frequency ranges—[0–0.7] GHz, [0–1] GHz, [0–1.5] GHz, and [0–1.7] GHz—were employed in an attempt to obtain signals at UHF sensors that fall within the typical frequency range for PD signal detection.

In the context of PD signals detection, their first peaks and extreme amplitudes in the first wave packets emerged earlier and with bigger magnitudes when employing the wider frequency ranges of Gaussian PD source input pulses. In the power station or transformer station, those signals will be simpler to detect at the four UHF sensors installed on the power transformer, as EFRs increase. TDOAs and the magnitude ratios between the extreme amplitudes in the first wave packets and the FPs of recorded signals at the sensors were shown to be useful for analysing the effects of PD wave reflections from the transformer's metal components on the signals. Since the magnitude ratios for signal 4 were the biggest for all EFRs, it was determined that signal 4 was the one most affected by the reflected PD waves. Since the TDOAs for signal 3 were the fewest for all EFRs, it was demonstrated that signal 3 was the one least affected by the reflected PD waves.

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Based on the obtained amplitude spectra of the signals at the sensors, it was shown that the total antenna efficiency and the internal structure of the transformer affect them. The amplitude spectra of recorded signals at four sensors were moved toward higher frequencies relative to the transmitting antenna's output excitation signals, for all EFRs.

Regarding PD source location, the best result was gained for the EFR of [0–1] GHz. Four factors might have affected it: 1) the weighted average frequency range of received signals at the sensors was the nearest to the weighted average frequency found from the total efficiency diagram of the receiving antennas, for the EFR [0–1] GHz; 2) more favourable TDOAs between FPs of the signals at sensors at [0–1] GHz EFR; 3) PD waves for the higher EFR of [0–1] GHz are less diffracted and attenuated when they hit transformer metal obstacles on their way from a PD source to the sensors than PD waves for the lower EFR of [0–0.7] GHz; 4) a smaller Delta S threshold was used in the simulation setup for the EFR [0–1] GHz as opposed to the EFRs [0–1.5] GHz and [0–1.7] GHz.

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